

Operational Stability and Safety of LDR Lite Under Extended Load-Following Conditions

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ABSTRACT

LDR lite is a small modular reactor concept for district heat production. Its design features, such as natural circulation and boron-free operation, pose unique challenges for flexible operation. In this study, two extended operational scenarios were calculated to assess the stability and safety of the reactor during load-follow conditions. The first scenario represents periodic power variation between 50 % and 100 %, while the second scenario is based on historical district heat demand and weather data from Helsinki, where both the power and network temperatures vary with outdoor temperature. The cases are calculated using process simulation software Apros coupled with 3D nodal neutronics solver Ants. In the control scheme, the secondary circuit temperatures remain constant while control rods are used to adjust the reactor power. Results show that the reactor tracks the power and temperature setpoints without instabilities in both scenarios. Key safety parameters, including temperatures, peaking factors and axial offset, show only minor increases from initial values suggesting that the fuel cooling and overall reactor safety are not compromised during load-follow operation with the selected control scheme. Future work includes optimization of the control as well as considering other states of the fuel cycle.

Keywords: SMR, LDR, district heating, load-following, natural circulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Load following is becoming an increasingly important topic particularly for small modular reactors (SMRs). More flexibility is going to be required in electricity production with the growing share of wind and solar power in the grid. In addition to electricity generation, SMRs are intended for various non-electric applications, which have their own needs for flexible operation. Examples include process heat and district heating, hydrogen production, desalination, and applications in space and marine industries.

In district heating networks (DHN), demand is highly dependent on the outdoor temperature with a base load determined by hot water consumption. Lower outdoor temperatures lead to higher power demand and vice versa. The network temperatures also vary depending on the outdoor temperature. When the outdoor temperature is low, both supply and return temperatures are high. Unlike electricity grid, district heating networks are small and localized, because the heat production must occur close to consumption. Nuclear reactors can be used for base-load production in bigger networks, but especially in smaller networks the need for load following is highlighted.

LDR lite [1] is a small light water reactor designed to produce low temperature heat in low pressure. The 50 MWth reactor operates without soluble boron and utilizes passive safety systems. The reactor is connected to a district heating network via secondary circuit and is designed for fully flexible district heat production.

This paper examines whether LDR lite can maintain operational stability and safety during extended load-following cycles. Two realistic load following scenarios are used as test cases. The analyses are

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conducted using Apros simulation software for the system thermal-hydraulics, coupled with nodal neutronics solver Ants for the 3D core power distribution. The system thermal-hydraulic response was studied earlier in [2]. Now, also the 3D neutronics are taken into consideration with a realistic control scheme to assess the whole system behavior from core all the way to the district heating network to capture all relevant phenomena.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Load Following Scenarios

Two different scenarios with a duration of one week are selected to challenge the load following capabilities of LDR lite. The first scenario, illustrated in Figure 1, assumes a regular day-night demand variation. The reactor operates on a fixed 24-hour cycle, during which the power level is reduced from 100 % to 50 % for nine hours once per day. The district heating network return and supply temperatures stay constant in this case. This pattern represent a hypothetical case of predictable load changes between day and night, and is used to evaluate the reactor's ability to handle routine power adjustments and their impact on system performance.

The second scenario, shown in Figure 2, is based on historical weather and district heating production data from Helsinki in 2017 [3]. The total heat demand is scaled down to represent a smaller district heating network. It is assumed that the network has two 50 MW reactors, with the simulated reactor responsible for all load following. The supply and return temperatures are derived from outdoor temperature data.

The selected case covers one week in January with cold days in the beginning and ending with more variable conditions. In the initial state, the reactor operates at full power and the district heating network temperatures are close to their maximum. Over the first few days, the required supply temperature decreases while the reactor remains at full power. This is followed by reduction in heat demand and daily fluctuations. This scenario is used to assess the reactor's capability to respond to realistic, weather-driven variations in district heating demand.

The reactor safety during load following is ensured by monitoring some key safety parameters, such as system temperatures and pressures, fuel and cladding temperatures, and power peaking factors as well as axial offset. The safety limits are not defined in the LDR lite specifications, but it can be assumed that the nominal state values should not be significantly exceeded during normal operation.

Figure 1. Boundary conditions for reactor power and district heating network temperatures during the first load-follow scenario with fixed 24-hour cycle.

Figure 2. Boundary conditions for reactor power and district heating network temperatures during the second load following scenario based on historical Helsinki weather and heat demand data.

2.2. LDR Lite

LDR lite [1] is a small district heat reactor designed to operate at low temperature and pressure. The primary coolant flow is driven by natural convection in the integral design. The design is self-pressurizing, which means that the primary pressure follows the core outlet temperature. There are two identical secondary circuit loops, which connect the primary circuit to the district heating network. The reactor vessel is enclosed inside a containment vessel, which is partly filled with water for passive decay heat removal. The whole reactor module is submerged in a pool.

The compact core has 37 truncated 17x17 pressurized water reactor (PWR) fuel assemblies and a heavy steel reflector. Control rods are located in each assembly, and they are divided into regulating groups and safety groups. The safety groups are located in the periphery of the core and middle assembly. The design does not utilize soluble boron during normal operation, so excess reactivity is compensated with control rods.

2.3. Computational Models

The analyses were performed using the Apros simulation platform in combination with nodal neutronics solver Ants. Apros, developed by VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd and Fortum, is a versatile process simulation tool that enables modeling of nuclear power plants, conventional power facilities, district heating networks and various industrial processes. Ants is a multi-group nodal neutronics solver developed at VTT. As a reduced-order neutronics solver in the Kraken framework [4] it is designed to handle steady-state, depletion, and transient calculations in rectangular, hexagonal and triangular nodal geometries [5, 6].

In the coupled setup, Ants solves the three-dimensional power distribution, while Apros calculates the thermal-hydraulic state of the system. The coupling was previously demonstrated and verified in [7].

For this work, the same input configuration is employed with the addition of the whole secondary circuit and district heating network in the Apros model. The Apros model includes the primary circuit, containment vessel, reactor pool, two secondary circuits modeled as one, and district heating network. The DHN return temperature is set in the model as an inlet boundary condition. The desired reactor power and DHN supply temperature are given to the model as setpoints.

The core is modeled with one flow channel for each assembly with no cross-flows. Both Ants and Apros have the same axial nodalization with 18 nodes for the active core and one node each for the top and bottom reflectors. In the radial direction Ants utilizes 2x2 subnodalization per assembly.

The core configuration is the first core loading specified in the benchmark [1]. The reactor is at the beginning of the cycle (BOC). This means that the regulating control rods are inserted deeply into the core for excess reactivity compensation skewing the power profile towards the bottom of the core.

Figure 3. Schematic figure of the Apros model nodalization of LDR lite (not in scale).

2.4. Control Scheme

There are many features, which make the LDR lite control for load following different from typical PWRs. The primary coolant flow is driven by natural convection, which means that the primary temperature and flow rate are dependent on each other and the reactor power, and cannot be directly controlled. Secondly, unlike other PWRs, there is no steam in the secondary circuit, which eliminates steam pressure as control variable. Thirdly, soluble boron is not used during normal operation, which means that the power control and excess reactivity compensation are both carried out with control rods.

Instead, the secondary circuit flow rate can be used for temperature control in the secondary circuit and indirectly in the primary circuit. The flow rate is controlled with the circulation pump speed and it is used to keep the hot leg temperature constant. The valve bypassing the DHN heat exchanger is used to control the cold leg temperature. Without this control, changes in the returning temperature in the DHN would reflect also on the cold leg temperature and all the way to the core inlet temperature causing reactivity changes in the core. In this analysis the cold leg temperature is kept constant, although small-scale power control could be performed with this valve.

The DHN return temperature is given to the model as inlet boundary condition. The mass flow in the district heating circuit is controlled so that the required supply temperature is reached at all times. This way the power extracted to the DHN follows the reactor power.

The reactor power is regulated using control rods, which are adjusted in 0.5 mm steps at predefined time intervals. At every interval, the reactor power is compared to the power setpoint. In case the power is too high, the control rods are inserted one step and if the power is too low, the rods are withdrawn one step. The interval between steps is 30 s, which allows time for the natural circulation system to adjust.

Controlled variable	Manipulated variable	Setpoint source	Control type
Hot leg temperature	Secondary circuit pump speed	Fixed setpoint	PID
Cold leg temperature	Bypass valve position	Fixed setpoint	PID
DHN supply temperature	DHN mass flow	Changing setpoint	PID
Reactor power	Control rod position	Load demand signal	Step-wise control algorithm

Table I. Control systems during the load-follow operation.

The tolerance limit for power adjustment is 1 %. All regulating rods are in the same position and are moved simultaneously, while the safety rods remain out of the core.

The control scheme was established and tested in [8]. The control scheme with all the controllers is described in Table I.

3. RESULTS

The results from the first scenario are presented in Figure 4. The reactor power follows the setpoint closely within the tolerance limit. When the power setpoint decreases, the control rods are inserted into the core to reduce power. The decreased power level leads to an increase in the xenon-135 concentration introducing negative reactivity. As xenon builds up, the control rods have to be gradually withdrawn instead to maintain the desired power level. To increase the power back to 100 % the rods are withdrawn further to compensate for the xenon poisoning. The xenon begins to burn off increasing the reactivity, and the rods are inserted again to prevent overshoot. Over time, the xenon concentration and rod positions settle into a steady oscillatory behavior in response to the changing power demand. The control rods move within a 5 cm range throughout the scenario. Since all regulating rods move simultaneously, the combined reactivity effect is significant, requiring only minimal adjustments. Therefore, the impact on parameters such as axial offset remains small.

The peaking factors do not increase significantly from the initial values. The axial offset is high already in the initial state, because at the beginning of cycle all the excess reactivity has to be compensated with the control rods, which causes the power to peak at the bottom. It increases only slightly during the transient, when the reactor power returns to 100 % as the xenon concentration is lower than in the initial state, and the control rods need to be inserted more increasing the axial offset. The maximum fuel and cladding temperatures do not increase during the simulation, which suggest that the cooling of fuel is not endangered at any point. The core outlet temperature and primary pressure do not increase from the initial state. The secondary circuit and DHN temperatures stay constant during the transient as intended.

The results from the second scenario are presented in Figure 5. Again, the reactor power setpoint is followed within the tolerance limit. Like in the first case, the core and fuel temperatures and primary pressure do not exceed the initial values and the peaking factors and axial offset increase only slightly. The secondary circuit temperatures remain constant. The DHN supply temperature follows the setpoint closely. Despite the irregular demand, the reactor operates in a stable manner without overshoots or instabilities. Even though the reactor power changes a lot, the rate of change is slow, which allows the reactor time to adjust.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper evaluated the load following capability of the LDR lite reactor under two extended operational scenarios. In both cases, the reactor successfully follows the power and supply temperature setpoints. The primary and secondary circuits behave in a stable manner without exceeding the initial temperature and pressure limits. The peaking factors and axial offset increase only slightly, and maximum fuel and cladding temperatures remained below the nominal state values, indicating that fuel cooling and overall reactor safety are not compromised during load following. Even with irregular demand patterns the system remains stable. This is likely aided by the slow rate of change in district heating load, which allows the reactor time to adjust.

Further research is needed, for example, to optimize the control rod movements and study the thermo-mechanical behavior of the fuel under cyclic conditions. Additionally, this study considered only BOC conditions, but also other states of the fuel cycle need to be taken into account to capture the full range of operational states.

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Figure 4. Main results from the regular load following scenario.

Figure 5. Main results from the irregular load following scenario based on historical weather data.